

Intramolecular π - π Interactions in Metal "Capped" Porphyrins

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Soret maxima of Zn(C_2 -Cap), Zn(C_3 -Cap) and Zn(TPP) were recorded in cyclohexane and toluene. In cyclohexane, a progressive red shift in the order, C_3 -Cap > C_2 -Cap > TPP, is observed. This is attributed to the intramolecular interaction between the porphyrin plane and the aromatic cap of the capped porphyrins. Accordingly, the steric hindrance to O_2 binding inside the cap is perhaps greater in C_3 -Cap than in C_2 -Cap. This is reflected in the lower oxygen affinity of Fe(C_3 -Cap)-(1,2-Me₂Im) relative to the C_2 -Cap analogue.

METAL complexes of "capped" porphyrins (Fig. 1), which are ortho-substituted tetraphenylporphyrins, have been prepared as model compounds for hemoglobin and myoglobin^{1,2}. The two capped porphyrins, C_2 -Cap and C_3 -Cap³, differ only by one methylene group in each of the four chains linking the aromatic cap to the porphyrin plane. It had been assumed that the "tight" C_2 -Cap would offer a greater steric barrier to the addition of O_2 inside the cap than would C_3 -Cap, but oxygenation studies of iron(II) complexes of C_2 -Cap and C_3 -Cap showed that Fe(C_3 -Cap)(1,2-Me₂Im) has a lower O_2 affinity than does Fe(C_2 -Cap)(1,2-Me₂Im)^{4,5}. Both capped complexes have a lower O_2 affinity than the Fe(TPP)(1,2-Me₂Im).

A [-(CH₂)_n-] n = 2 C_2 -Cap
n = 3 C_3 -Cap

Fig. 1. Zinc(II) "capped" porphyrins.

Porphyrins and metalloporphyrins have been shown to have a tendency to π -complex to π -donors and acceptors and even to aromatic hydrocarbons such as toluene⁶⁻⁹. We suggest that the aromatic cap in the capped porphyrins too have the potential to solvate the porphyrin. Our studies indicate that the two aromatic planes in C_3 -Cap have greater π - π interaction than does C_2 -Cap, suggesting that the aromatic planes are closer together in C_3 -Cap, perhaps due to the greater flexibility of the longer straps in this molecule. Evidence in support of this is provided by the observed red shift in the Soret maxima of Zn(II) complexes of C_2 -Cap and C_3 -Cap relative to Zn(TPP).

Experimental

Zn(TPP), Zn(C_2 -Cap) and Zn(C_3 -Cap) were prepared following the methods of Baldwin and co-workers¹⁰ from the free bases and characterized by mass spectrometric analysis. Aldrich spectrophotometric grade cyclohexane was stored over Linde 4A molecular sieves. Reagent grade toluene and benzene were distilled under N_2 from sodium benzophenone ketyl.

Spectra of the Zn(Por) complexes in cyclohexane, benzene and toluene were recorded at room temperature on a Cary Model 14 UV-visible spectrophotometer using quartz cells with a 1 cm path length.

Results and Discussion

The Soret maxima of Zn(C_2 -Cap) and Zn(C_3 -Cap) in aromatic and nonaromatic solvents are presented in Table 1. These may be compared with the corresponding values for the open complex, Zn(TPP), as reference. Due to limited solubility of the complexes in cyclohexane, suitable high concentrations could not be obtained for significant absorbance in the visible region.

TABLE 1—SORET MAXIMA OF ZINC PORPHYRIN COMPLEXES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Zn(Por)	Position of Soret band (nm) in		
	Cyclohexane	Benzene	Toluene
Zn(TPP)	416	423.5	423.5
Zn(C_2 -Cap)	419	423.5	423.5
Zn(C_3 -Cap)	424	424	424

In order to look at the π - π interactions between the aromatic top of the cap and the porphyrin plane in absence of axial ligands and solvent interactions, the noncoordinating and nonpolar solvent cyclohexane was used. The spectra show (Table 1) that the Soret band of C_3 -Cap has been red shifted by 5 nm with respect to C_2 -Cap, and the shift is 8 nm in comparison with TPP. For TPP and C_2 -Cap there is a red shift in the aromatic solvents, whereas C_3 -Cap does not exhibit any difference between

aromatic and nonaromatic solvents. Soret maxima of metal complexes of porphyrins are sensitive to differences in groups at the periphery of the porphyrin ring, in axial ligands and in solvents¹¹. Lewis acid-base interactions of metalloporphyrins with neutral ligands cause a red shift in this spectral characteristic, and the shift increases directly with the magnitude of interaction^{12,13}. Taking zinc mesoporphyrin IX dimethyl ester in cyclohexane as the reference (Soret 397 nm), Corwin and co-workers¹⁴ observed a red shift of 5 nm in toluene for this compound. A variety of nonpolar solvents also cause similar red shifts due to adduct formation¹⁵. Interestingly, π -donors as well as π -acceptors shift the Soret band in the same direction.

Based on these observations and considering the aromatic nature of the cap, it seems reasonable to ascribe the red shifts in these compounds to π - π interaction between the porphyrin and the aromatic top of the cap. The extent of this interaction in C_2 -Cap is perhaps equivalent to the interaction between TPP and toluene. Hence in toluene, Zn(TPP) has a maximum which is the same as that for Zn(C_2 -Cap) in all the solvents.

A comparison of the Soret band positions of C_2 -Cap and C_3 -Cap with that of TPP shows, at least qualitatively, that the intramolecular π - π interaction is greater in Zn(C_3 -Cap) than in Zn(C_2 -Cap). This is in accord with the observation^{4,5} that the O_2 affinity of Fe(C_2 -Cap)(1,2-Me₂Im) is greater than that of the corresponding C_3 -Cap complex, and that both have a lower dioxygen affinity than does the open analogue complex, Fe(TPP)(1,2-Me₂Im).

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3. Abbreviations: C_2 -Cap, dianion of the capped porphyrin, 5,10,15,20-[pyromellitoyl(tetrakis-*o*-oxyethoxyphenyl)]porphyrin; C_3 -Cap, dianion of the capped porphyrin, 5,10,15,20-[pyromellitoyl(tetrakis-*o*-oxypropoxyphenyl)]porphyrin; TPP, dianion of meso-tetraphenylporphine; Por, dianion of a porphyrin; 1,2-Me₂Im, 1,2 dimethylimidazole.
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